

FORMOWANIE PROFESJONALNIE WAŻNEJ JAKOŚCI OFICERÓW NA PRZYSZŁOŚCI W SYSTEMIE AKTYWNOŚCI «MAN-MAN» I «MAN-MECHANIZM»

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Streszczenie. W artykule przedstawiono specyfikę studiowania zawodowo istotnych cech przyszłych oficerów okrętowych. Pokazano, że kształtowanie zawodowo istotnych cech przyszłych specjalistów od statków odnosi się jednocześnie do systemu działania «człowiek-człowiek» i «człowiek-mechanizm». Analizowany jest problem rozwoju poziomu kompetencji zawodowych i menedżerskich. Zidentyfikowano siedem głównych grup umiejętności i kompetencji niezbędnych oficerowi statku do skutecznej działalności zawodowej: optymalizacja istotnych cech w procesie zarządzania, tworzenie zjednoczonego zespołu, analiza problemu i argumentacja decyzji, wymiana informacji z podwładnymi, wspieranie dyscypliny pracy i władzy wykonawczej, motywowanie własnej aktywności zawodowej i zbiorowej, racjonalna organizacja własnej działalności zawodowej. Określono następujące obszary kompetencji przyszłych oficerów okrętowych: wykonywanie funkcji zawodowych, ocena i kontrola działalności zawodowej podwładnych, organizacja zadań zawodowych podwładnych, zapewnienie odpowiedniego poziomu motywacji podwładnych, przygotowywanie i wdrażanie decyzji zarządczych, komunikatywnych: wymiana informacji, podejmowanie decyzji, organizacja własnej działalności zawodowej i wspieranie niezbędnego poziomu aktywności zawodowej, zapewnienie szkoleń dla podwładnych. Udowodniono, że jest wiodącym źródłem skutecznych działań zawodowych działalność jest osobowością przyszłego oficera statku oraz jego umiejętności i umiejętności w zakresie organizacji zasobów ludzkich i materialnych i technicznych. Udowodniono, że przyczynia się do sukcesu przyszłej działalności zawodowej nabyte profesjonalnie znaczące cechy, które powinny rozwijać się pod wpływem nauczania dyscyplin społecznych i humanitarnych. Udowodniono, że proces edukacyjny powinien stanowić podstawę do krytycznej oceny ich życia i doświadczenia zawodowego, świadomość wyboru sposobu i metod poprawy osobistych i zawodowych cech; umiejętność krytyki i samokrytyki, wytrwałość w osiąganiu celu, zainteresowanie jakością przyszłych działań zawodowych, umiejętność podejmowania odpowiedzialności, podejmowania decyzji, umiejętność efektywnej pracy w zespole, umiejętności komunikacyjne, umiejętności integracyjne, samoregulację, samodoskonalenie osobowości zawodowej w połączeniu z aktywnością zawodową, ustawianie i rozwiązywanie zadań zawodowych, rozwiązywanie problemów, samostanowienie, samorealizacja, samodoskonalenie.

Słowa kluczowe: profesjonalnie istotne cechy przyszłych oficerów okrętowych, system działania «człowiek-mężczyzna» i «człowiek-mechanizm», rozwój zawodowy, kompetencje zawodowe i menedżerskie, profesjonalizm, szkolenia zawodowe, dyscypliny społeczne i humanitarne.

FORMING OF FUTURE MARITIME OFFICERS` PROFESSIONALLY SIGNIFICANT QUALITIES IN THE «HUMAN-HUMAN» AND «HUMAN-MACHINE» INTERACTION SYSTEMS

Abstract. The article presents the peculiarities of future maritime officers` professionally significant qualities. It is shown that the formation of future maritime specialists` professionally significant qualities refers to the system of «human-human» and «human-machine» interaction simultaneously. The problems of the professional level and the managerial competence are

analyzed. Seven main groups of skills and competences which are necessary for a maritime officer for the successful professional interaction are identified: optimization of significant qualities in the process of management activity, formation of a united team, analysis of the problem and the decisions taken argumentation, exchange of information with subordinates, support of labor and executive discipline, motivation of own professional activity and the collective ones, rational organization of their own professional interactions. The spheres of future maritime officers competence are as follows: performance of professional functions, assessment and control of subordinates` professional interaction, subordinates` organization of professional tasks, motivation of subordinates, preparation and implementation of managerial decisions, communicative qualities: information exchange, decision-making, organization of own professional interaction and maintaining the necessary level of professional interaction, providing training for subordinates. It is proved that the main factor of effective professional interaction is the personality of the future maritime officer and his skills plus abilities in the organization of human and technical resources. It is noted that the success of the future professional interaction contributes to the acquired professionally significant qualities, which should be developed under the influence of social and humanitarian disciplines. It is pointed, that the educational process should lay upon the foundations for a critical assessment of own life and professional experience, awareness of choosing the ways and methods for improving personal and professional qualities; ability to criticism and self-criticism, persistence in achieving of the goal, interest in the quality of future professional interaction, ability to take responsibility, decision-making, team-working, communicative skills, integration skills, self-regulation, self-development of a person in combination with professional interaction, professional tasks solving, problem situations solving, self-determination, self-realization, self-improvement.

Key words: professionally significant qualities of future maritime officers, «human-human» and «human-machine» interaction systems, professional development, professional and managerial competence, professionalism, professional training, social and humanitarian disciplines.

Introduction. Scientific and technological progress sets the new requirements for the level of professional competence and managerial culture of future specialists in the maritime industry. Today the essence and mechanisms of human interaction, priorities of vital values and ideals, and the role of personality in society are fundamentally changing. All these factors require a high level of future maritime officers` management and professional competence.

Such innovative way of the professionally significant qualities formation refers to the system of «human-human» and «human-machine» interaction systems simultaneously (*Klimov, 1996*).

Formation of the personality lasts all his life, and the period of study at high school plays a special role in this process. In this time future specialists get the foundations of their professionally significant qualities, which will help to enter into a new environment of his professional interaction, in which his further development as a personality and socialization will take place. Therefore, the question of the future maritime officers` personal formation in the aspect of their professional interaction should be at the center of the higher education attention. To do this, the system of teaching and learning process should be built on the basis of the harmonious development of future maritime officers both as individuals and as future specialists.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the formation of professionally significant qualities of future maritime specialists in "human-human" and "human-machine" systems, to disclose the concept of professional and managerial competence.

Main part. The personality of future maritime officers is multifaceted and multifaceted. Maritime officers are the category of workers who are the professionally manage people, perform their own functional duties and work in a team, they are responsible for the safety of others, whose activities are aimed at the final result and material liability. In addition, their activities will be related to an isolated environment, work in the system of «human-human» and «human-machine». Maritime officer is a professionally trained specialist who organizes people's work on the basis of regulatory documentation, which defines the exact boundaries of their functional responsibilities in microsystems.

According to the topic of our study, it is important to find out different approaches to define the concepts of «professional development», «professional competence» and «managerial competence».

B. Ananiev and O. Sannikova, analyzing theories of the individual, emphasize the preconditions for professional development:

1) the success of professionalization is determined by the degree of individual and psychological characteristics to the requirements of the chosen profession;

2) the level of individual psychological characteristics compliance with professional requirements is determined by interest to the chosen profession;

3) professionalization is a long-term process that lasts throughout the professional life and takes place at certain periods, stages and is characterized by a change in professional requirements against the background of professional career;

4) the content of the correlation of the individual-psychological composition, abilities and requirements of the profession, taking into account the completeness, intensity and specificity, determines the professional and psychological development of the personality, progressiveness or regressivity, taking into account/ignoring his orientation, intensity etc.;

5) professional development of the individual cannot be considered without taking into account mental motility, operative and other psychological qualities and processes, since they are not a one-time process;

6) the orientation of the individual is a determining psychological factor in the professional selection of future professionalism;

7) the attitude to the profession is determined by the level of its development, taking into account professional, physiological, medical, social and other factors, which directly influence the labor and vital activity of the individual (Ananiev, 1974; Sannikova, 1995).

Thus, according to V. Slastonin and other scholars, professionalism is the professional competence of a manager, which is defined as the unity of his theoretical readiness to carry out his activity. The content of theoretical readiness consists of analytical, predictive, projective and reflexive skills, organizational and communicative skills are belonged to practical readiness. Also, in the opinion of the author, professional-management competence is the ability of the manager as a subject of managerial influence, capable of redefining scientific and practical knowledge (Nesyn, 2010, p.12).

V. Maslov understands the competence of the head as the system of theoretical and methodological, normative provisions, scientific knowledge, organizational, methodological and technological skills that are necessary for the person to perform his duties (Maslov, 2002, p. 64).

According to I. Zyazun, competence is a special type of knowledge organization that enables effective decision making (Ziaziun, 2001, p. 79).

The analysis of different approaches to the definition of competence in general suggests that most researchers associate it with the concept of a professional interaction, with a specific profession in the material and spiritual spheres. Competence is the ability to perform actual activities (Lokshyn, 2015).

V. Lokshin reveals the professional competence of the management specialist through the prism of theoretical and practical readiness for management and creative interaction and characterizes the level of his professionalism. In addition, the main competence structure is the numerous skills that characterize this readiness (Lokshyn, 2015).

The leading resource of effective professional interaction is the personality of the future maritime officer and his skills, abilities in the organization of human and technical resources. The personality of the future maritime officer should work out and consolidate professionally meaningful qualities under the number of factors.

In this connection, an analysis of managerial professional competence is relevant. The issue of competence of the manager is associated with professionalism, and therefore the category of «professional competence» will be determined by the level of professional education and experience, also be individual abilities and qualities of the leader, motivated by the desire for continuous self-education and self-improvement, creative and responsible attitude to the case (Nesyn, 2010, p.13).

The success of a maritime officer depends on the level of his management competencies. The educational process of a higher educational institution in the formation of professionally significant qualities of future maritime officers should be aimed at stimulating the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities, the acquisition of professionally necessary information, the specification of individual and personal development, the achievement of both social and professional status, the development of self-control skills, self-regulation and self-improvement, understanding of the professional behavior specifics, ability to work on those problems that interfere with the development of professional experience, knowledge, skills and abilities. Hence, the quality of the work of future maritime officers depends to a large extent on the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in the educational process of the higher educational institution, aimed at achieving professional self-realization and providing professional reliability in the context of their future activities.

Consequently, the professionalism of manager is seen as the result of conscious deliberate activity, which involves a certain level of professional competence of the head.

As A. Filippov points out, there are attempts to divide the definition into management activity and managerial competence. The latter should be considered as a kind of management activity, its component is related to the organization of cooperation, which is based on common interests. «In general, management is the process of developing, adopting and implementing managerial decisions. It is a kind of professional activity aimed at optimization of activity with the help of economic, administrative, psychological and pedagogical influences, which value orientations, positions, installation of personality, groups, directs and activates, increases the efficiency of professional activity» (Filippov, 1990, p. 117).

Consequently, the managerial competence of future maritime officers should include:

1) deep and meaningful knowledge of the professional sphere - knowledge of the mechanisms and features of their actions, knowledge of the electrical part of the vessel, the ability to navigate and safety equipment;

2) knowledge, skills and abilities of managerial interaction and work with subordinates.

The managerial competence of the manager is a complex concept that cannot be reduced to management abilities, to education in the field of management psychology, or to personal qualities of the individual, because in this case the understanding of opportunities turns out to be one-sided.

Psychological and pedagogical bases of managerial (professional) competence formation are determined by:

- a set of qualities and personality characteristics, determined by a high level of psychological training;

- high level of professional preparedness for management activity and effective interaction in the process of working in a team with a teaching staff that can be considered as a system of manager's internal resources which are necessary for the productive work.

Only in these circumstances, the maritime officer will be able to achieve the effective professional activities of the entire crew.

Professionally significant qualities of future maritime officers should include professional knowledge, skills and abilities that meet the important professional criteria for future activities: the presence of purely professional knowledge, skills and abilities that are identified only in a situation that relates directly to professional activities and is reproduced mentally or physically actions under any conditions; knowledge and fulfillment of the future officer duties must meet certain attestation criteria of their activities, which are regulated by the requirements of the service; the ability to study and self-study, self-improvement and self-development, to the accumulation of professional experience and its implementation in future professional activities; ability to act in non-standard situations; state of physical fitness; efficiency; look and feel; knowledge of working with documents, culture of work with educational materials.

L. Sergeeva, studying the quality of future specialists from the point of practical psychological direction, argues: the division of responsibilities takes into account the individual characteristics; the speed of orientation in situations requiring the practical use of the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in dealing with «affairs-people» and «people-affairs» situations; management of the psychological state according to the conditions of professional interaction; the ability to find ways and means of solving current issues; «accounting» of relationships, own sympathies and antipathies, psychological differences in the implementation of joint activities. It is pointed in future professional interaction to observe ethical-deontological norms: a sense of measure in the process of interaction with the environment; language adaptation to different people, «lack of language template»; communication skills depending on their individual psychological characteristics; feeling of a situation; taking into account external factors that may affect professional interaction; sensitivity, attentiveness, endurance, tolerance in relationships; relaxedness, naturalness in communication, the ability to remain always in oneself in relationships with people, lack of insolence, deliberate behavior; the sense of justice, the objectivity of the approach to those who organize, the ability to show and prove this objectivity. This concerns the organizational skills of future professionals (*Sergeeva, p. 32*).

In addition, the author considers the significant personality as to have an emotional and volitional sphere that promotes opportunities to influence others, mobilize, unite, group and guide their joint efforts to achieve common goals. Ability to emotionally-volitional action includes social energy, demanding and critical. In particular, social energy includes the following indicators: emotional and communicative influence, which is manifested in various emotional forms of speech, intonation - high tone, flexibility, timbre of voice, accents and pauses; volitional induction, manifested in the linguistic, mimic and pantomime form - a gesture, a look, a posture, an expression of the face. Possession of the linguistic function of volitional induction is expressed in the ability of the organizer to use many verbal forms - request, coercion, advice, call, conviction, demand, order, order, etc.; the ability to influence others with their attitude to the environment, affairs, events, situations; the logical persuasiveness of the word influence and the ability to reveal the causal relationship, prove the logical sequence in the speech and practical activity forms; self-confidence, optimism, correct and quick choice in solving a difficult situation and relevance and justification of risk, courage and perseverance (*Sergeyeva, p. 33*).

Demand as a characteristic of the person is expressed in such indicators as: courage and consistency of requirements, their persistent, permanent character; flexibility of requirements depending on the situation; independence of requirements, their casual nature; categorical, indisputable; a variety of requirements, the ability to expose them in the form of a joke, a witty remark, sarcasm; individualization of requirements depending on the personal emotional state and the environment. Indicators of criticality are: critical observation as the ability to see and identify shortcomings; independence of criticality; logic and argumentation of critical remarks, critical analysis; frankness and courage; the depth and severity of criticisms of deficiencies; benevolence (*Sergeyeva, pp. 34*).

Also L. Sergeyeva analyzes leadership qualities that are essential for future professionals - purposeful formation and deepening of the corresponding qualities and skills: the development of personal motivation, a strong desire to be a leader, self-confidence, readiness to make decisions and take responsibility; development of individual intellectual and moral leadership qualities, professional competence, decency, developed intellect; ensuring the social competence of the leader and his benevolence in relations with the members of the group - the culture of communication, the ability to express clearly, to properly listen to the employees, to make comments, to give advice, to be attentive, to support colleagues; the acquisition of skills and abilities to quickly and correctly assess the situation, to know and take into account the peculiarities, interests, needs and expectations of the team (*Sergeev, pp. 34-35*).

So the analysis of the literature gives opportunity to define seven groups of skills and abilities required by a maritime officer for a successful professional interaction. Pic.1.

The maritime officer should anticipate the exchange of information with subordinates and management: written orders and reports; holding briefings; personal communication. In addition, the issue of labor and executive discipline support should remain in the field of view: to bring to the subordinates professional requirements and safety in the process of interaction; control over the fulfillment of the functional duties; the formation of organizational qualities that consolidate the necessary models of work and the adoption of administrative penalties and incentives.

Pic. 1. Main groups of skills and abilities, required by a maritime officer for a successful professional interaction

The maritime officer is motivated for professional interaction and is responsible for motivating the work of his subordinates: the ability to inspire subordinates to achieve the goal, the ability to use the means of material and moral stimulation, creating of motivating conditions and ensuring the level of satisfaction of subordinates, their desire to work in the team. The maritime officer provides a rational organization of his own work: planning his own time; planning of professional self-realization; the ability to maintain a high level of efficiency and overcome the negative effects of stress.

The emphasis of social and humanitarian disciplines is placed on the fact that theoretical and practical training should be realized in the future professional interaction of maritime officers.

The success of future professional interaction contributes to the acquisition of professionally significant qualities which must be developed under the influence of teaching social and humanitarian disciplines: responsibility, demanding, uncompromising, professional competence. Disciplines of the social and humanitarian cycle in the formation of future maritime officers' professionally qualities are strategically important.

Social and humanitarian disciplines, combined with training, are designed to develop professionally relevant qualities which are necessary for further implementation in future interaction of maritime officers.

After analyzing the above, we can distinguish the following areas of future maritime officers' competence:

- performance of professional functions;
- assessment and control of the subordinates professional interaction;
- organization of professional tasks performance;
- ensuring the level of subordinates motivation;

- preparation and implementation of managerial decisions;
- communicative qualities: information exchange, decision making;
- organization of own professional interaction and maintenance of the necessary level of professional interaction;
- training of subordinates.

Thus, the technical training carried out in accordance with the curriculum provides purely professional training, and social and humanitarian disciplines provide the opportunity to form the psychological and pedagogical qualities that are important in the process of interaction with human factors. However, modern requirements for a future specialist require skills and practical skills for acquiring knowledge, the formation of professionally significant qualities of future maritime officers.

As the learning process changes constantly, it is intended to facilitate successful adaptation to the newly formed team, readiness for future professional interaction - knowledge, skills, abilities, professional competence, activities in an isolated environment and in extreme conditions.

So, the educational process takes into account the needs of modern seafaring, where professional qualities are important. Maritime officers should lay the foundations for a critical assessment of his life and professional experience, awareness of the choice of ways and methods for improving personal and professional qualities; ability to critique and self-criticism, persistence in achieving the goal, interest in future professional interaction, ability to take responsibility, decision-making, ability to work effectively in a team, heuristics, communicative skills, integration skills, self-regulation, self-development in conjunction with professional interaction, solving professional tasks, solving problem situations, self-determination, self-realization, self-improvement, self-affirmation, developing ethical-deontological standards, ability to plan and control of studying, initiative, perseverance; skills for drawing up a basic and advanced professional plan.

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